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AI multilingual tools for social innovation: new perspectives on civic technologies, digital empowerment and inclusive governance

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Civic technologies are increasingly promoted as tools to enhance democratic participation, decision-making, collective action, and digitally enabled governance. This study examines the emergence of AI-enabled multilingual civic platforms and their potential to support inclusive participation and social innovation in linguistically diverse democracies. The study adopts a conceptual and exploratory research design, supported by qualitative analysis, to enhance the theoretical clarity of contested concepts such as digital empowerment and social innovation. A systematic review of 158 civic technology platforms was also conducted to examine the role and limitations of major public resource repositories in promoting multilingual democratic processes through three dimensions: social innovation, digital democracy, and civic technology. The findings show that instrumentalist approaches to social innovation – prioritising efficiency, performance, and scalability of civic tools implementation – predominate over approaches that emphasising empowerment, deliberation, and changes in social and governance relations. Most platforms are technology-driven rather than human-centered, with limited attention to inclusion, linguistic diversity, and meaningful participation. Consequently, their capacity to enable transformative forms of social innovation remains constrained. The study concludes that while AI-enabled multilingual platforms may reduce language barriers and facilitate the participation of minority and vulnerable groups, their democratic and socially innovative potential depends on the alignment between technological and user design, governance arrangements, and the extent to which they enable inclusive participation and knowledge co-creation.

KEYWORDS

AI tools, civic empowerment, digital democracy, inclusive governance, multilingual democracy, social innovation

1 Introduction

Encompassing the fast advances of digitalisation and emergent technologies, a substantial body of research has examined the increasing use of digital tools to support civic engagement and improve citizens' participation in political life (de Gil Zúñiga et al., 2010; Boulianne, 2020; Zhang et al., 2022; Raj et al., 2025; Shin et al., 2024; Rymon, 2026). Terms such as “civic technology” and “Democracy Technologies (DemTech)” linked to “e-participation”, “digital

democracy”, “digital deliberative democracy”, and “e-democracy” have been introduced to frame these phenomena (Mäkinen, 2006; Schrock, 2019; Lindner and Aichholzer, 2020; Detthamrong et al., 2025; Sarafis et al., 2025). Civic technologies (CT) are generally understood as platforms and applications that enable citizens to connect, deliberate, and collaborate with each other as well as with public institutions, thereby expanding opportunities for participation and co-creation in democratic processes (Boehner and DiSalvo, 2016; Berg and Hofmann, 2021; Goñi, 2025). Digital platforms have become ubiquitous arenas of public debate, reshaping relationships between citizens and democratic institutions while redefining how governance, participation, and civic agency are enacted in digital contexts (Chadwick, 2003; Dawes, 2008; Zuiderwijk et al., 2021; Umbach and Tkalec, 2022; Karkin and Cezar, 2024; Sujaryanto and Al Rasyid, 2025). Several authors conceptualise digital platforms and online deliberation as complementary governance tools, embracing “the apparent tension between *technologising democracy* and *democratising technology*” (Goñi, 2025, p. 1955). The exponential research on AI, including machine learning, natural language processing, computer vision, generative models, and data-driven predictive systems, as well as their rapid integration into contemporary societies has become central to debates on governance, policymaking, and democratic life (De Sousa et al., 2019; Duberry, 2022; Bentley et al., 2024; Gaudeul et al., 2025; Guridi et al., 2025; Kahl, 2025). The surge in regulation, alongside increasing public and private investment, underscores the scale and accelerating pace of this transformation (Kuziemski and Misuraca, 2020; Mesarčik and Slosiarová, 2025; Liang, 2026). At the same time, these developments pose profound challenges to democratic governance, transparency, accountability, and the evolving social contract between citizens and the state (Savaget et al., 2019; Tessler et al., 2024; Petit and Oleart, 2025). Recent scholarship highlights that the evolution of AI in civic technologies extends beyond initial deployment and basic accessibility. Current debates focus on deeper institutional integration, algorithmic accountability, and the socio-technical impacts of generative tools on pluralistic societies, reflecting the growing complexity of AI-enabled governance (Floridi et al., 2018; Mittelstadt, 2019). This shift underscores the need to examine not only technological efficiency but also how AI intersects with inclusion, linguistic diversity, and participatory governance in multilingual civic platforms. AI-enabled systems are increasingly envisioned as a strategic instrument to strengthen participatory democracy, offering “new avenues to re-enchant democracy and overcome some of its most pressing challenges” (Duberry, 2022, p. 195). They are seen as enhancing efficiency, transparency, and security while supporting new forms of civic engagement (Gherghina et al., 2021; Detthamrong et al., 2025; Gaudeul et al., 2025; Rymon, 2026). Several authors emphasise the growing capacity of AI and digital technologies to process large volumes of structured and unstructured data, enabling the large-scale synthesis of citizen inputs and facilitating governance responses aligned with the pace and complexity of contemporary societal challenges, particularly in urban environments (Certoma, 2022; Duberry, 2022; Guridi et al., 2025; Sarafis et al., 2025). These technologies are increasingly associated with new forms of civic empowerment, as they may enable individuals and communities to develop the skills, confidence, and agency required to engage more actively in democratic and governance processes (Mäkinen, 2006; Friess and Eilders, 2015; Sujaryanto and Al Rasyid, 2025; Tour and Creely, 2025). Raj et al. (2025), for example, highlight how AI-driven decision-making systems, Big Data analytics, and generative AI tools are transforming political participation by enabling predictive modelling, generating

behavioural insights, and supporting automated policy processes. Bennett and Segerberg (2023) further argue that these transformations are reshaping political engagement through evolving social practices and new forms of digitally mediated collective action. At the same time, the literature points to persistent challenges related to access, equity, and representation (Zuiderwijk et al., 2021; Androusoπούλου et al., 2024; Detthamrong et al., 2025; Raj et al., 2025; Sarafis et al., 2025).

Despite the proliferation of civic technologies and their often optimistic portrayal, significant limitations remain in both scholarship and practice (Aichholzer and Rose, 2020; Sieber et al., 2025). Savaget et al. (2019) highlight a notable research gap concerning how AI-based technologies and public data disclosure may contribute to civil society empowerment. Much of the existing literature tends to emphasise technical affordances—such as accelerating information flows, reducing participation costs, or enhancing government responsiveness—while paying insufficient attention to core democratic concerns, including equity, freedom of expression, representation, and genuine empowerment (Boulianne, 2020; Larsson, 2021; Androusoπούλου et al., 2024; Guridi et al., 2025). Aspects like who benefits from these innovations, whose voices remain excluded, and how linguistic diversity shapes access to civic participation are frequently neglected (Desmet et al., 2020; Gherghina et al., 2021; Erdocia, 2023). Moreover, the assumption that digitalisation alone fosters inclusion disregards persistent structural inequalities, including the digital divide, trust, and political efficacy (Larsson, 2021). Against this backdrop, the present study is guided by the following research questions:

- How do AI-enabled multilingual platforms reshape theoretical understandings of civic technology by foregrounding inclusion, linguistic diversity, and digital empowerment?
- To what extent do civic technologies make the integration of AI, multilingualism, and contextual sensitivity explicit, observable, and operational in relation to digital empowerment and social innovation?

By addressing these questions, this study tackles a neglected area in digital democracy scholarship, namely, how linguistic diversity intersects with digital participation and empowerment. The contribution is twofold: (a) to explore the state of the art in civic technologies and AI-enabled multilingual platforms, focusing on their role in promoting inclusive participation, digital democracy and social innovation (Misuraca et al., 2018; Certoma, 2022); and (b) to offer useful insights on inclusive civic technologies capable of responding to the challenges of pluralistic societies to advance in the sustainability transition (Wirtz et al., 2019; OECD, 2023; Sieber et al., 2025).

2 Civic technologies and digital democracy as arenas of digital and transformative social innovation

2.1 Civic technology: literature overview

Over the past four decades, civic technology has emerged as an expanding research field that captures how universities, public institutions, and civic actors leverage technology to address societal challenges and strengthen democratic engagement (Dawes, 2008; Justice et al.,

TABLE 1 Civic technologies: main research streams and thematic focus.

Research stream	Core focus	Representative literature
E-democracy/digital democracy/deliberative e-democracy	Democratic participation, representation, legitimacy, and deliberation in digital contexts	Chadwick (2003), Dahlberg (2011), Berg and Hofmann (2021), Hernández (2025), and Ohren et al. (2026)
Citizenship, online participation, and e-participation	Civic engagement in policy processes, citizen–government interaction, participatory mechanisms	Macintosh et al. (2009), Susha and Grönlund (2012), Wirtz et al. (2018), Santini and Carvalho (2019), Faganello and Luciano (2023), Ruess et al. (2023), Karkin and Cezar (2024), and Shin et al. (2024)
E-deliberation, knowledge co-production and democratic innovation	Digitally mediated deliberative processes, collective sense-making, and co-production of knowledge. This strand comprises the Large-Scale Group Decision-Making (LSGDM), a rapidly evolving field focused on digital platforms and collective decision scenarios	Coleman and Moss (2012), Friess and Eilders (2015), Aitamurto and Landemore (2016), Ma et al. (2025), and Ohren et al. (2026)
Digital empowerment and digital citizenship	Citizens' capacities, agency, inclusion, and skills for meaningful participation	Mäkinen (2006), Mossberger et al. (2007), Savaget et al. (2019), Pangrazio and Sefton-Green (2021), and Tour and Creely (2025)
E-government/digital government	Digital transformation of public administration and public service delivery	Moon (2004), Heeks and Bailur (2007), Janowski (2015), Malodia et al. (2021), and Benlahcene et al. (2024)
E-governance/digital governance	Coordination, accountability, and networked governance arrangements in digital environments, including regulation and ethical issues	Dawes (2008), Bindu et al. (2019), Umbach and Tkalec (2022), Waheduzzaman and Khandaker (2022), Hanisch et al. (2023), Detthamrong et al. (2025), Dunleavy et al. (2006), and Liang (2026)
Digitalisation and AI adoption in public administration	Organisational, institutional, and policy implications of ICT and emerging technologies in the public sector	Dawes (2008), De Sousa et al. (2019), Kuziemski and Misuraca (2020), Göksan (2023), Madan and Ashok (2023), Mountasser and Abdellatif (2023), and Hammerschmid et al. (2024)
Civic tech movements, community technologies, and digital activism	Bottom-up civic engagement, community-driven technologies, participatory design, e.g., human computer interaction (HCI)	Townsend (2013), Boehner and DiSalvo (2016), Schrock (2016, 2019), McNutt (2017), Aragón et al. (2020), Barandiaran et al. (2024), and Fusi et al. (2026)
AI and emerging technologies in civic technologies (cross-cutting)	AI, NLP, blockchain, and immersive technologies applied across democratic, administrative, and governance domains	Al-Mushayt (2019), Androutsopoulou et al. (2019, 2024), Liu et al. (2019), Razzaq et al. (2019), Wirtz et al. (2019), Kshetri et al. (2024), and Sarafis et al. (2025)

2018; Bindu et al., 2019; Zuiderwijk et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022). The literature is highly fragmented and spans multiple disciplinary traditions and analytical level. Including information systems (IS), computer and computational social science, design science, public administration, political studies, urban planning, sustainability, and innovation studies (Heeks and Bailur, 2007; Aragón et al., 2020). Table 1 shows the main research streams that have shaped the field, identifying their core thematic focus and representative contributions.

While holistic perspectives on civic technologies and citizen involvement have recently emerged at the intersection of urban development, social innovation, and sustainability literatures, these contributions remain fragmented, under-theorised, and largely disconnected from existing research streams. Unlike the streams summarised in Table 1, this literature does not fit neatly into a single category, as it spans multiple disciplines and analytical levels, framing civic technologies as sociotechnical infrastructures embedded in broader processes of urban transformation, collective problem-solving, and sustainability transitions (Townsend, 2013; Misuraca et al., 2018; Saldivar et al., 2019; Wilson and Chakraborty, 2019; Saßmannshausen et al., 2021; Raj et al., 2025; Sieber et al., 2025; Tariq et al., 2025). Recent attention has also focused on the geography of the digital divide and biases in civic technology design, especially regarding the disruptive role of generative AI and other emerging technologies (Shortall et al., 2021, 2022; Bentley et al., 2024; Hughes

et al., 2025; Sieber et al., 2025; Zhang and Wang, 2025; Zidouemba, 2025).

Despite the richness of these research streams, the coexistence of multiple disciplinary perspectives has contributed to conceptual ambiguity regarding the meaning, scope, and societal role of civic technologies. Civic technology is broadly defined as “the use of technology for the public good” (Sifry et al., 2017, cited by Schrock, 2019).¹ However, this definition obscures differences in underlying assumptions, design, and governance models (Shortall et al., 2021). It encompasses general-purpose social media platforms, such as Facebook or TikTok, as well as purpose-built civic applications (Androutsopoulou et al., 2019; Aragón et al., 2020; Alarabiat et al., 2021). As a result, civic technology has increasingly been used as an umbrella term describing a wide range of digital initiatives developed by civil society organisations, public institutions, private actors, and citizens (Justice et al., 2018; Santini and Carvalho, 2019; Zhang et al., 2022; Ramiro Troitiño and Mazur, 2024). Government-led initiatives include attempts by city governments to resist corporate control and build digital public infrastructures. A prominent example is Barcelona’s “New Data Deal,” which seeks to reclaim data as commons and introduces procurement and data sharing standards

¹ Various authors mention that the term appeared in a report by the Knight Foundation.

(Fernandez-Monge et al., 2024). From a different angle, Justice et al. (2018, pp. 89–90) describe civic technology as “a technology-led social movement that promises to transform the relationships among technology, the nonprofit and commercial sectors, and government”, which “involves voluntary action (both online and off-line) and nonprofits” and “represents the nexus of several related trends (i.e., self-organization, leaderless organisations, social media/Web 2.0, open source software development, etc.) as well as a set of situations that have created the opportunity for collaboration among sectors facilitating the growth of new partnerships and perspectives.”

Ambiguity also emerges in the distinction between e-government—a narrow institutional focus on ICT to improve service efficiency and accessibility (DeBenedictis et al., 2002; Moon, 2004)—and e-governance, which emphasises cooperative relationships, networked coordination, and ICT-supported deliberation among government, citizens, civil society, and private actors (Misuraca et al., 2018; Certoma, 2022; Hammerschmid et al., 2024). E-government is often treated as a subset of e-governance, which extends to participatory processes, deliberation, and shared decision-making (Dawes, 2008; Bindu et al., 2019). Research over the past two decades shows how successive waves of technological innovation—from early web-based services to contemporary AI and immersive technologies—have progressively reshaped administrative practices and governance arrangements (Ho, 2002; Moon, 2004; Göksan, 2023; Hammerschmid et al., 2024; Raj et al., 2025). Similarly, research on e-participation and e-deliberation appears to be fragmented, dispersed across disciplinary silos, and relatively under-theorised (Macintosh et al., 2009; Susha and Grönlund, 2012; Benlahcene et al., 2024).

A widely cited report by the Knight Foundation defines civic technologies as tools “used to inform, engage and connect residents with government and one another to advance civic outcomes” (Patel et al., 2013). It distinguishes two clusters of civic technology platforms: *open government*, for transparency, data utility, decision-making, feedback, and voting; and *community action*, for crowdfunding, community organizing, information crowdsourcing, forums, and peer-to-peer sharing. The latter foregrounds bottom-up dynamics, empowerment, collective action, and alternative participation outside formal institutional channels (Aragón et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2022).

Zhang et al. (2022) argue that the widespread adoption of ICTs has intensified debates around the meaning and practice of participatory and deliberative democracy, prompting governments to implement e-consultation platforms and online feedback mechanisms. Digital tools have scaled institutional innovations such as mini-publics and participatory budgeting, giving rise to a distinct research agenda on digitally mediated deliberation (Strandberg and Grönlund, 2014; Karkin and Cezar, 2024).

More recent scholarship situates civic technologies within broader deliberative and governance frameworks, conceptualising e-governance as a socio-technical environment that enables new forms of interaction, accountability, and collaboration at the intersection of public administration reform and wider societal transformations, including the pursuit of the Sustainable Development Goals (David et al., 2017; Tariq et al., 2025). Accordingly, civic technology initiatives can emerge either through top-down governmental strategies or through bottom-up forms of civic action. Government-led initiatives include attempts by city governments to resist corporate control and build digital public infrastructures.

Social innovation perspectives consider that civic technologies extend beyond technical affordances or administrative functions,

emphasising the transformation of social relations, practices, and governance arrangements that address societal challenges and enhance collective agency (Avelino et al., 2017; Misuraca et al., 2018; Aragón et al., 2020; Certoma, 2022). In this view, civic technologies become socially innovative not simply because they digitise participation, but because they enable new forms of interaction, deliberation, and co-creation between citizens and institutions, with the potential to reshape power relations and democratic practices (Savaget et al., 2019; Barandiaran et al., 2024). This perspective resonates with broader European policy debates on digital democracy, inclusion, and the triple transition, which emphasise the role of ICT-enabled participation and open access to information in advancing green, digital, and social objectives, while placing equity, wellbeing, and inclusion at the core of digital transformation strategies (OECD, 2023; Ramiro Troitiño and Mazur, 2024). Empirical studies across European contexts further suggest that e-participation and digital democracy initiatives are increasingly intertwined with broader processes of social and institutional innovation (Hennen et al., 2020; Certoma, 2022).

2.2 Civic technology: instrumental versus transformative perspectives

Overall, the literature reveals a persistent tension between instrumental and transformative understandings of civic technologies (Table 2). A recent survey of civic technology for social innovation shows this dichotomy in academic literature, between government-centric definitions, e.g., “use of technology by cities for service provision, civic engagement, and data analysis to inform decision making,” and citizen-centric definitions, e.g., “platforms and applications that enable citizens to connect and collaborate with each other and with government” (Saldivar et al., 2019).

Instrumental approaches focus on efficiency gains, improved information flows, and service optimisation, often aligned with administrative modernisation agendas and performance-oriented governance models (Wirtz et al., 2019; Androutsopoulou et al., 2024; Hughes et al., 2025). Transformative perspectives, by contrast, emphasise empowerment, inclusion, and shifts in power relations, questioning whether civic technologies genuinely expand democratic agency or merely repackage existing hierarchies in digital form (Dahlberg, 2011; Barandiaran et al., 2024; Sieber et al., 2025). In this respect, digital agency is recognised as central to an “individual’s ability to control and adapt to a digital world” (Passey et al., 2018, p. 426).

Situating civic technologies within e-governance as a dynamic and open socio-cultural and technical system allows these tensions to be analytically productive. In this sense, civic technologies and digital democracy can be understood as arenas of transformative social innovation, where competing visions of participation, governance, and public value are negotiated rather than predetermined. This tension becomes particularly salient in linguistically diverse democracies, where civic participation is shaped not only by access to digital technologies, but also by language, cultural capital, and political efficacy. While civic technologies are often presented as vehicles for broader inclusion, empirical research consistently shows that their benefits are unevenly distributed, frequently reproducing or even amplifying existing social and political inequalities (Boulianne, 2020; van Dijk, 2020). Language thus emerges as a critical yet under-theorised dimension of digital democracy and social innovation, especially in the context of increasingly data-driven and AI-enabled civic platforms.

TABLE 2 Civic technologies through instrumental and transformative lenses.

Dimension	Instrumental perspective	Transformative perspective
Main goal	Improve efficiency, transparency, and delivery of public services	Reconfigure power relations, democracy, and civic engagement
Role of technology	Functional tool to optimize existing processes	Sociotechnical medium to enable structural change
Role of citizens	User or client of digital services	Rights holder, political actor, co-creator of policy
Type of participation	Consultative, reactive, or limited (voting, passive feedback, reporting, e-services)	Deliberative, co-creation/co-production, shared decision-making
Relationship with the state	State as efficient service provider (top-down)	State as facilitator or partner (bottom-up/hybrid)
Social innovation process	User & community centered	Collaborative and more practices and systems-centered
Inclusion	Assumed or indirect (those with access participate)	Explicit and central (attention to digital, linguistic, and socio-cultural gaps)
Success measured by	Adoption, usage, speed, cost reduction	Capacity-building, (digital) empowerment, equity, institutional change
Main risks	Technocratization, exclusion, “participation washing”	Conflicts, slow implementation, institutional resistance

Source: own elaboration.

3 Civic technologies, AI-enabled multilingualism and digital empowerment

Building on the tensions identified in the literature, this section focuses on language as a neglected dimension of participation and empowerment, and how recent advances in AI-enabled multilingual systems create both opportunities and risks for inclusive civic engagement in increasingly diverse societies (Kalampokis et al., 2024; Sarafis et al., 2025; Verhasselt, 2025). Various researchers emphasise concepts such as knowledge co-production, co-creation, collective intelligence, and collaborative governance, particularly in relation to deliberative processes (Skaržauskienė, 2022; Lee-Geiller, 2024). However, these approaches often implicitly conceptualise “the citizen” as part of relatively homogeneous publics, treating diversity as an add-on rather than as a constitutive feature of democratic participation. When diversity is addressed, it is frequently framed through isolated categories (e.g., migrants or people with disabilities) rather than as an intersecting and systemic condition of contemporary societies. Moreover, research has shown that civic technologies have historically paid limited attention to vulnerable or marginalized groups (Schrock, 2016; Peixoto and Fox, 2017; Gherghina et al., 2021; Larsson, 2021). This gap becomes particularly evident in the European context, where public administrations face growing challenges in integrating diverse populations (Katsarova, 2022; Erdocia, 2023; Gaudeul et al., 2025). Language constitutes a primary barrier, functioning not merely as a tool of communication but as a gateway to culture, rights, and political participation. As Kraus and Frank (2022) underline, democratic engagement is fundamentally grounded in communication: language is intrinsic to voting, consensus-building, will-formation, and collective decision-making. In multilingual societies languages operate not only as instruments of interpersonal communication but also as carriers of identity, history, and power relations.

Although Europe’s linguistic pluralism is often celebrated as a cultural asset, it poses significant challenges for democratic inclusion and effective policymaking, particularly for vulnerable and minoritized groups. The European Union has formally committed to linguistic diversity through Article 22 of the *Charter of Fundamental Rights* and related instruments, such as the *European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages* and the *Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities*. More recently, this commitment has been

operationalized in initiatives such as the Conference on the Future of Europe (CoFE), which relied on a digital platform to enable citizen participation across all official EU languages (European Commission, 2022; Seubert, 2024). Despite these policy efforts, research on linguistic justice in the digital public sphere demonstrates that insufficient multilingual accessibility in civic and governance platforms exacerbate existing inequalities (Erdocia, 2023; Gaudeul et al., 2025).

The expansion of AI and rapid digital transformation of democracy further intensifies these challenges. While language technologies such as automatic translation, subtitling, and community-based applications offer opportunities to enhance accessibility and visibility, digital platforms and AI systems frequently reproduce linguistic hierarchies, privileging dominant languages and marginalizing others (Saldivar et al., 2019; Santini and Carvalho, 2019; Duberry, 2022; Hughes et al., 2025; Verhasselt, 2025). As scholarship on technodemocracy highlights, digital infrastructures often embed epistemic exclusions unless multilingualism is explicitly integrated into their design. Recent advances in AI, particularly in natural language processing (NLP) and machine translation, are introducing new dynamics (Kedrova and Potemkin, 2025). AI-enabled multilingual systems have the capacity to process, translate, and synthesize large volumes of citizen input across languages, potentially lowering long-standing linguistic barriers to participation (Zuiderwijk et al., 2021; Duberry, 2022; Sarafis et al., 2025). These tools are frequently framed as opportunities to revitalize democratic processes by making participation more inclusive, scalable, and responsive, particularly in contexts characterised by migration, multiculturalism, and linguistic plurality. However, critical researchers caution against techno-optimistic narratives, emphasising that AI systems are embedded in socio-technical assemblages shaped by institutional priorities, data availability, and algorithmic design choices (Helbing et al., 2023; Gaudeul et al., 2025), which may inadvertently reproduce existing power asymmetries. Unequal access to digital skills and varying levels of trust in institutions can further constrain the empowering potential of AI-enabled participation (Boulianne et al., 2023). Raj et al. (2025) also highlight that AI tools have not yet been well integrated into existing platforms and frameworks for civic engagement, which are commonly rooted in outdated, inefficient or inherently unrepresentative approaches for gathering public inputs.

From a social innovation perspective, the key question is therefore not whether AI can enable multilingual participation, but under what conditions such technologies contribute to transformative rather than

merely instrumental forms of digital democracy. This requires analysing AI-enabled civic platforms as socio-technical spaces where technological capabilities intersect with governance models, institutional openness, and civic cultures. In line with the triple transition framework (OECD, 2023), digital transformation must be co-created with society and grounded in democratic participation, fairness, and cultural as well as linguistic diversity, rather than treated as a purely technical or efficiency-driven endeavor (Lee-Geiller, 2024). Nevertheless, it remains unclear to what extent these concerns are systematically integrated into the design and implementation of civic technologies. Empirical research addressing this issue remains extremely limited. For instance, Shin et al. (2024) examined 116 digital tools for citizen participation, yet, like many existing studies, their analysis does not explicitly assess whether or how AI-enabled multilingual and linguistically inclusive perspectives are operationalized in civic platforms and applications. To address this gap, the following section outlines the methodological approach adopted to analyse a selected sample of civic technologies.

4 Methodology

4.1 Methodological approach and empirical design

A conceptual research design is employed, supported by qualitative analysis to enhance conceptual clarity and theoretical robustness, particularly in relation to complex and contested constructs (Maxwell and Mittapalli, 2010; Alvesson and Sandberg, 2011). The methodological approach is explicitly exploratory and critical, aiming to assess not only the presence of technological features, but also the extent to which these features are made explicit, operational, and normatively aligned with digital empowerment and social innovation. The sources include academic literature, practitioner-oriented publications, and existing repositories of civic technology platforms. This multi-source strategy allows for triangulation between scholarly discourse, and platform-level practices, which is particularly relevant given the normative claims often associated with AI, multilingualism, and participation.

4.2 Dataset construction and selection criteria

The empirical strategy follows a two-stage sampling approach: (a) an initial baseline dataset was constructed through an internet-based search of $N = 116$ civic technology tools referenced in Shin et al. (2024). This initial corpus was subsequently screened and, (b) the dataset was expanded and updated through a review of major public repositories, the repositories consulted were: (a) Civic Tech Field Guide,² (b) People Powered³ (global hub for participatory democracy), (c) AirTable civic tech repository,⁴ (d) Democracy Technologies,⁵ (e) Participedia.⁶ This process resulted in an initial sample of $N = 182$ civic technology platforms. A subsequent screening led to the

exclusion of several platforms due to insufficient publicly available information, inactivity at the time of analysis, or a lack of relevance to civic or political participation (e.g., Alto al Didymo and Flu Near You). The final analytical sample consisted of $N = 158$ platforms/apps, reflecting both consolidation and expansion during the iterative review process. Table 3 shows the analytical categories considered.

5 Results

The analysis shows a significant expansion of civic technology platforms since the late 2000s, with a marked acceleration after 2010. This temporal distribution points to the emergence of a flourishing market for democratic technologies at local, regional, national, European, and international levels (see Annex). The geographical distribution has a strong concentration of civic techs in the United States ($N = 24$), as well at European level ($N = 9$) or operating at global level ($N = 10$). However, this expansion contrasts with the uneven development of deliberative depth, inclusivity, and empowerment (see Table 4). Many private-sector civic technology platforms operate primarily as service providers to public administrations, supporting voting and citizen engagement tools embedded within E-government or smart city logics. They offer modular participation services—such as surveys, idea collection, and feedback aggregation—frequently commissioned by municipalities to enhance consultation and administrative responsiveness. While these platforms contribute to scaling participation, their design tends to prioritise efficiency, data aggregation, and manageability over deliberative depth or shared decision-making. By contrast, platforms developed by third-sector or hybrid organisations, e.g., social enterprises, are more likely to support deliberation and knowledge co-production, frame participation around collective challenges, and experiment with alternative governance models. Notable examples include Decidim, Consul, Adhocracy, CitizensOS, YourPriorities, Loomio, and Polis, which explicitly embed deliberative mechanisms, transparency features, and, in some cases, normative commitments to democratic deepening. Nevertheless, despite the presence of these more transformative initiatives, the overall landscape remains dominated by platforms created by private companies and oriented towards instrumental participation models, where civic engagement is framed primarily as a service to support public-sector decision-making rather than as a process of citizen deliberation or empowerment (see Table 4).

The analysis reveals a strong imbalance in the types of participatory functions and social innovation supported by these platforms. While a large majority refer problem or needs identification (80.3%) and solution identification (74.3%), only 52 platforms (32.9%) explicitly support knowledge co-production or co-creation. Marketing narratives highlight co-construction of policies (39.2%), but references to decision-making processes are limited (50%). This sharp drop indicates that collaborative knowledge generation remains marginal within the civic tech landscape. Overall, participation mechanisms linked to collective decision-making are unevenly developed across platforms. While 63 applications (39.9%) incorporate voting functionalities, many of these are specialised tools dedicated solely to this purpose, rather than integrated into broader participatory processes. Deliberation is claimed by 55 platforms (34.8%), and interactive modes of participation are also unclear, with only 32 platforms (20.3%) including real-time communication, suggesting a limited

2 <https://app.civictech.guide/tools>

3 <https://www.peoplepowered.org/>

4 <https://airtable.com/>

5 <https://democracy-technologies.org>

6 <https://participedia.net/>

TABLE 3 Analytical dimensions.

Dimension	Analytical focus	Key questions
General characteristics	Type of founder (public administrations and governmental institutions; business/private sector; NGOs/third sector; other) Place of creation (country) Scope (local, European, international) Year of creation	What general characteristics do the platforms exhibit?
Mode of participation	Information, consultation, deliberation, including polls/surveys, open suggestions/feed-back, voting, co-funding, and participatory budgeting	What forms of participation are enabled?
Social innovation orientation	Problem identification, solution development, knowledge co-production, policy co-construction	How do the platforms support social innovation processes?
Inclusion and equity	Accessibility, minority representation, vulnerable groups included	Which groups are explicitly included or implicitly excluded?
Empowerment logic	Efficiency-driven vs. agency-driven participation	Are citizens positioned as contributors, co-creators, or decision-makers in deliberation processes?
Languages coverage	Monolingual, two languages, several languages	What is the primary language of the platform?
	Multilingual and contextual cultural sensitivity	Is multilingualism treated as a technical feature or as a mechanism for inclusion and empowerment?
AI integration	Mention of AI integration, e.g., NLP, machine translation, summarisation, etc.	Is AI explicitly acknowledged?

TABLE 4 Characteristics of civic technology applications.

Aspect analysed		N	%
Founder/s	Private-sector	95	60.1
	Third sector/civil society	39	24.7
	Public sector/government	24	15.2
Social innovation orientation	Problem/needs identification	127	80.3
	Solution identification	116	73.4
	Decision-making	79	50.0
	Mention of co-construction of policies	62	39.2
	Knowledge co-production/co-creation	52	32.9
Inclusion and equity/mention of empowerment		53	33.5
Mode of participation	Citizens open suggestions/feed-back	110	69.6
	Survey/Polls	94	59.5
	Voting	63	39.9
	Deliberation/collaborative decision-making	55	34.8
	Real time communication	32	20.3
	Fundraising/Participatory budget	28	17.7
	Cofunding	17	10.8
Language coverage	Local orientation (monolingual applications)	59	37.3
	Multilanguage support/translation	39	24.7
	Two languages	26	16.5
AI integration	AI/Generative AI	20	12.7
	Speech recognition	5	3.2

N: number of civic technologies (total N = 158).

adoption of mechanisms that foster genuine engagement and co-creation. Cofunding mechanisms such as crowdfunding ($N = 17$, 10.8%) and participatory budgeting ($N = 28$, 17.7%) are represented by platforms with an explicit social and environmental innovation

orientation in urban planning and smart cities development. Many private-sector platforms operate as service providers to governments to support urban planning and to facilitate citizen engagement tools embedded in e-government or smart city logics (e.g., Co-urbanize,

ArcGISHub, Dipas). These results suggest that most civic technologies prioritise low-intensity forms of participation such as consultation, voting, and feedback collection, while support for deliberation, co-creation, and shared decision-making is still limited. This pattern reinforces an instrumental model of participation, in which citizen input is collected and processed, but rarely translated into collective knowledge production or empowered decision-making.

Notably, 53% of the applications represent local developments, as evidenced by the use of a single language or, in some cases, availability in only two languages, predominantly English. Only 39 applications (24.7%) explicitly support multilingualism, mostly reflecting market expansion rather than genuine attention to multicultural environments. With a few exceptions, such as Decidim and Consul, multilingual support is not systematically considered and associated with platforms that claim to enable co-creation, deliberation, or knowledge co-production. Overall, the analysis reveals that social innovation is present mainly in an instrumental form rather than substantive approach to inclusion: participation is technically open, but linguistically and culturally constrained. From an empowerment perspective, mentioned together inclusiveness by 33.5% of platforms/apps, minorities, migrants, and disabled people are practically not considered.

The AI integration in civic technologies remains limited and generally not natively implemented. In our sample, 12.7% of applications report AI or generative AI features, and 3.2% include speech recognition. Some platforms, such as Decidim, Consul, Go-Vocal, and Assembl, enable AI functionalities indirectly—for example, via machine translation services—supporting multilingual participation.⁷

6 Discussion

6.1 Revisiting RQ1: AI-enabled multilingual platforms and theoretical assumptions on civic technology

From a theoretical standpoint, civic technologies, and particularly those incorporating AI, are framed as enablers of expanded participation, capable of lowering barriers and fostering more inclusive democratic processes. Multilingualism is frequently highlighted as a mechanism to address structural exclusions embedded in linguistic dominance and national policy cultures. However, our empirical analysis reveals that this theoretical promise is only partially realised. Only a small subset of platforms integrates multilingual functionalities in a meaningful way, and even then, these features are often add-ons rather than embedded principles of platform design.

Situating these findings within the instrumental versus transformative framework (Section 2.2, Table 2) shows that most AI-enabled platforms adopt an instrumental approach: AI and multilingual features are deployed primarily to optimize participation, improve administrative efficiency, and scale engagement, rather than to redistribute power or enable co-creation. By contrast, transformative approaches—evident in platforms such as Decidim or Consul—integrate multilingualism as a mechanism for empowerment, deliberation,

and knowledge co-production, aligning technological capabilities with democratic deepening. Furthermore, this pattern echoes critiques in e-governance and deliberative democracy literature (Friess and Eilders, 2015; Larsson, 2021; Karkin and Cezar, 2024), showing that while procedural access is expanded, epistemic inclusion, deliberative influence, and collective agenda-setting remain limited.

Rather than transforming civic technology paradigms, AI-enabled multilingualism currently operates within narrow procedural frameworks: it broadens access without necessarily redistributing voice, influence, or epistemic authority. Linguistic diversity is thus recognized at the interface level but rarely connected to broader notions of digital empowerment, understood as the capacity of individuals and communities to shape agendas, co-produce knowledge, and influence policy outcomes. These findings expose a persistent tension between normative expectations of inclusion and empowerment and the practical design choices of civic technologies, reinforcing critiques of participatory platforms as often limited in democratic depth. Theoretically, this underscores the need for civic tech scholarship to engage critically with language, power, and epistemic justice, rather than assuming that technological sophistication automatically yields inclusion.

6.2 RQ2: operationalising AI, multilingualism, and contextual sensitivity in practice

The second research question examined to what extent civic technologies make the integration of AI, multilingualism, and contextual sensitivity explicit, observable, and operational in relation to digital empowerment and social innovation. Here, the findings are more conclusive and point to significant limitations. The analysis shows that AI functionalities are often implicit, opaque, or narrowly oriented towards efficiency. When present, AI functionalities tend to be oriented towards efficiency rather than towards enhancing deliberative quality, intercultural dialogue, or contextual problem framing. Similarly, multilingualism is rarely designed with sensitivity to cultural, political, or contextual differences, reinforcing a standardised, scalable model of participation rather than a situated, empowering one. Linking these findings to the literature on digital empowerment and co-creation (Mäkinen, 2006; Friess and Eilders, 2015; Berg and Hofmann, 2021; Certoma, 2022; Tour and Creely, 2025), it becomes evident that while platforms claim to support collaborative innovation, few enable citizens to meaningfully influence decision-making or institutional outcomes. This gap highlights the distinction between participation as a procedural or instrumental act versus participation as a form of transformative social empowerment.

In relation to social innovation and digital social innovation, the findings reveal a clear imbalance between early-stage engagement (problem identification and solution ideation) and deeper forms of innovation involving co-production of knowledge and co-construction of policies. While many platforms claim to support collaborative innovation, only a minority enable citizens to engage meaningfully in decision-making processes or to influence institutional outcomes. This limits the transformative potential of civic technologies and confines social innovation to consultative or experimental spaces, detached from governance structures. Our analysis shows that digital empowerment is framed as participation without power, confirming concerns raised in the social innovation literature regarding the instrumentalisation of participation and the depoliticisation of civic engagement through digital tools. This suggests that digital participation can

⁷ A dedicated repository of AI civic technologies exists (<https://directory.civictech.guide/listing-category/artificial-intelligence>) but was not included in this sample, as most of these platforms do not natively support multilingual processes.

reproduce existing hierarchies rather than enabling structural change (Barandiaran et al., 2024; Sieber et al., 2025).

7 Conclusion

This study critically examined whether contemporary civic technologies advance more inclusive, empowering, and socially innovative forms of participation. By explicitly integrating theoretical frameworks with empirical findings, several key conclusions emerge: First, while AI-enabled multilingual platforms hold significant potential to reshape civic technology by addressing linguistic exclusion and enhancing inclusion, this potential is largely unrealized in practice. Multilingualism is rarely embedded as a foundational design principle linked to empowerment, and AI is predominantly used to optimize processes rather than to deepen democratic engagement. As a result, civic technologies can continue to reproduce existing power asymmetries, rather than challenging them.

Second, the study demonstrates that the integration of AI, multilingualism, and contextual sensitivity is neither explicit nor systematic across platforms. These elements are seldom operationalized in ways that support transformative social innovation or meaningful digital empowerment. Instead, civic technologies largely reinforce instrumental, government-adjacent, and efficiency-driven participation models, privileging consultation over deliberation and co-creation.

Taken together, the findings contribute to ongoing debates on civic technology and social innovation by highlighting the need to move beyond technological solutionism. They underscore the importance of reconceptualising civic tech as a socio-technical and political infrastructure, where language, context, and power relations are central rather than peripheral concerns. For future research and practice, this implies a shift towards embedding multilingualism as a democratic, not merely technical feature; attention to design of AI systems that enhance deliberative quality and epistemic diversity; and the alignment of civic technologies with transformative social innovation agendas, particularly in relation to governance and sustainability transitions. In doing so, civic technologies could move to enabling digital empowerment, and contributing meaningfully to build democratic and societal transformation.

From a theoretical perspective, the study highlights the need to overcome fragmentation across research traditions, as civic technology scholarship, social innovation studies, and sociotechnical approaches have largely evolved with limited conceptual integration. Bridging these fields offers significant potential to better understand civic technologies as infrastructures of transformative social innovation rather than merely as participatory tools. In doing so, civic technologies could move beyond facilitating digital participation to enabling genuine digital empowerment and contributing meaningfully to democratic and societal transformation.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/[Supplementary material](#), further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Author contributions

ME-S: Writing – original draft, Resources, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Supervision, Investigation, Data curation, Methodology. CL: Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization, Validation, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Methodology, Resources, Data curation.

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Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Generative AI statement

The author(s) declared that Generative AI was used in the creation of this manuscript. AI tools were used to support language editing and clarity of expression. No AI system was used to generate data, conduct the analysis, or produce research findings.

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Supplementary material

The Supplementary material for this article can be found online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpos.2026.1792788/full#supplementary-material>

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